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Authentic Development Some Gandhian Criteria

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Abstract: Though Gandhi was no economist, a deep inner voice told him: “You are on the right track, move neither to your left nor right, but keep to the straight and narrow way” in his understanding of economics and development. Outlining the meaning of four key notions of Gandhi (satya, ahimsa, svadeshi and swaraj), the author outlines a Gandhian idea of development based on freedom and concerned about the marginalized people. Gandhi believed that India can help the world to acquire a different vision of life and development. Thus Gandhi wished to see India developing into a paradigm case where the basic human needs are satisfied.

Keywords: Gandhi, satya, ahimsa, svadeshi and swaraj, non-violence, advaita, well-being, freedom.

Of late one hears a lot about “India’s emergence as a fast-growing economic power.”¹ India’s “growth rate is now approaching that of Asia’s other economic juggernaut, China.”² This, however, is not the full truth.

Prosperity and progress haven’t touched the 550,000 villages where two-thirds of India’s population live... Millions of women are not getting the education they need. Transportation networks and electrical grids, which are crucial to industrial development and job creation, are so dilapidated [that] it will take many years to modernize them.³

Writing in 1908, Gandhi made a statement that today comes across to us as prophetic: “The generally accepted principles of economics are

invalid. If acted upon, they will make individuals and nations unhappy. The poor will become poorer and the rich richer...” (CW 8.371).⁴

The success of a recent movie “Lage Raho Munnabhai”, portraying Gandhian ideals, is an indication that Gandhi continues to have an appeal to people even today. Even though all of us may not always follow his advice, he can still challenge us. He may impart to us some wisdom that may guide us in our struggle to become a developed nation. Gandhi was no economist: “I know very little of economics” (EW 93). He was even advised that, given his ignorance, he ought to stop “experimenting in matters of economics at the expense of the public” (EW 93). Yet a deep inner voice tells him: “You are on the right track, move neither to your left nor right, but keep to the straight and narrow way” (EW 93). I believe that our inner wisdom can sometimes give us a deeper understanding of human growth and development than formal studies can do.

A. Satya: The Goal of Development

Gandhi makes clear his purpose in writing his autobiography, *The Story of My Experiment with Truth*: to share with others the insights of his many years of spiritual striving, i.e., “to see God face to face, to attain Moksha” (Au x). For him ‘God is Truth’ is not merely a theoretical statement, but the driving force of his life, giving it a direction and unity: “I live and have my being in pursuit of this goal. All I do by way of speaking and writing and all my ventures in the political field are directed to this same end” (Au x). The integration he experienced was not merely imposed from outside by the one purpose of his life—satya, but also experienced from within because “truth is the sovereign principle, which includes numerous other principles” (Au xi). “The word *satya* is derived from *sat*, which means that which is. *Satya* means a state of being” (EW 231). Thus truth (satya) is above all a mode of being: being what we should be, an experience of wellbeing.⁵ Hence satya must be the goal of development. Only then will development be authentic.

Advaita: Well-being as an Experience of Integration

To understand Gandhi’s approach to development we need to appreciate the basic presupposition of his thought. Though not an

Advaitin in the traditional sense, Gandhi believes in some kind of *advaita*, “in the essential unity of man and for that matter of all that lives,” and as a consequence, “if one man gains spiritually, the whole world gains with him and, if one man falls, the whole world falls to that extent” (CW 25.390). A contemporary writer puts it more tersely: “Poverty anywhere is a threat to prosperity everywhere.”⁶ Gandhi suggests some kind of symbiotic relation binding the whole of creation, a creation held together by “the universal and all-pervading Spirit of Truth” (Au 420). Thus, there is a certain oneness, a certain non-duality in all reality, because all reality comes from, is sustained by, and finds its fulfilment in the Real, in Truth. The whole of creation mediates the presence of “the one and the same Creator” (Au 230).

Humans do not have independent goals. “One’s respective *dharma* towards one’s self, family, nation and the world cannot be divided into watertight compartments” (EW 183). Like Gandhi, we too are called to see God face to face, and all our undertakings are to be directed to this goal. What is actually happening is just the opposite. “The predominant character of modern civilization is to dethrone God and enthrone Materialism” (CW 28.127). The deepest dimension of being human—our openness to transcendence—is put aside. “The flesh has taken precedence over the spirit” (CW 48.442). Carried away by the more popular understanding of development we “make bodily welfare the object of life” (HS 23). For Gandhi *advaita*, being an ontological principle, becomes an existential ideal: human life must be an experience of integration. “There must be a return to simplicity and proper proportions” (HS 23).

When we put aside our quest for the supreme Truth, as the ultimate end, and, therefore, the normative goal of human life, we become victims of materialism,

all the while conveniently forgetting that its greatest achievements are the invention of the most terrible weapons of destruction, the awful growth of anarchism, the frightful disputes between capital and labour and the wanton and diabolical cruelty inflicted on innocent, dumb, living animals in the name of science, ‘falsely so called’” (EW 83).

Development is authentic only when it promotes the total well-being of persons, who constitute a just society and maintain the integrity of creation.

The Well-being of Persons

To be wholesome persons we need to have health of body, peace of mind, and joy in our health. Good health is the greatest wealth. “We must search for wealth not in the bowels of the earth, but in the hearts of men. If this is correct, the true law of economics is that men must be maintained in the best possible health, both of body and mind, and in the highest state of honour” (CW 8.325). Hence “economics that ruins one’s health is false, because money without health has no value. Only that economy is true which enables one to conserve one’s health” (CW 60.268). To be healthy we need to take care of the basics of life. “Every human being has a right to live and therefore to find the wherewithal to feed himself and where necessary [if need be] to clothe and house himself” (EW 94).

Peace of mind is essential for good health. A disturbed mind leads to many psychosomatic diseases. “Ignoring the emotion is to forget that man has feelings” (CW 61.250). Inner joy and peace is much more important than all the forms of pleasure the consumer market promises us. The family is the primary source of our emotional well-being. It provides us with our first experience of belonging, of being wanted and cared for. Yet, sad to say

more than any other institution, it has been affected by the profound and rapid changes witnessed by the world today. Many families are struggling to live in fidelity to authentically human values, while some others have become totally bewildered. Some even doubt if the institution has any purpose at all.⁷

The life-styles that emerge from being part of a developed society tend to minimize our human interactions.

We’ve forgotten the magic of sharing a meal with our family members... it is also important to remember that sharing a meal is not just about eating, but also about strengthening family bonds and making pleasant memories... The more often families eat together,

the less likely that kids are going to smoke, drink, do drugs or get depressed.⁸

Any development that tends to undermine the family in unhealthy.

Many “economists do not take men’s conduct into account but estimate prosperity from the amount of wealth accumulated and so conclude that the happiness of nations depends upon their wealth alone” (CW 8.371). But humans have an ethical dimension. Therefore “True economics must follow ethics. Even if we fail in this we shall have succeeded” (CW 62.241).⁹ As long as we continue to be ethical we have not failed. An ethical collapse would mean the end of our humanity. Any development that makes money the primary concern is detrimental to our well-being. “Rome suffered a moral fall when it attained high material affluence. So did Egypt [suffer a moral fall] and so perhaps most countries of which we have any historic record” (EW 95). Moral decadence is suicidal. Yet, this is happening even today “Western nations today are groaning under the heel of the monster-god of materialism. Their moral growth has become stunted” (EW 97). On the other hand moral discipline gives us power. “When we can be certain that once the spirit of discipline comes to pervade our lives, we shall be able to get anything we may want” (EW 103).

If we are not ethical in our personal life, then we cannot claim to have integrity in other areas of life.

I am firmly of the view, and it is my experience too, that, if a person has violated a moral principle in any one sphere of his life, his action will certainly have an effect in other spheres. In other words, the belief generally held that an immoral man may do no harm in the political sphere is quite wrong. And so is the other belief that a person who violates moral principles in his business may be moral in his private life or in his conduct in family affairs” (EW 181-82).

Without morality, development can only be distorted. Morality is not merely avoiding evil. We need to cultivate positive attitudes.

Love is a rare herb... and this herb grows out of non-violence... We should act only through love; thus alone shall we succeed. So long as we do not have unshakable faith in truth, love and non-violence, we can make

no progress. If we give up these... we shall be doomed
(*CW* 14.299-300).

The Well-being of the Society

The development of persons cannot be confined to the well-being of individuals. “Not the good of the few, not even the good of the many, but it is the good of all that we are made [by God] to promote, if we are ‘made in His own image’” (*CW* 61.250). The vast majority of the people of India live in “about half a million villages.”¹⁰ Only when the village economy prospers will India prosper. We need to encourage the villagers “to revive their lost industries and arts by assuring them a ready market... If we neglect our duty to our villagers, we shall be courting our own ruin” (*CW* 60.256).

Wealth has a social function. Gandhi tries to explain this by giving two examples: “The circulation of wealth among a people resembles the circulation of blood in the body... the concentration of blood at one spot is harmful to the body and, similarly, concentration of wealth at one place proves to be a nation’s undoing” (*CW* 8.303). The more the wealth is distributed the better it serves society. On the other hand accumulation of wealth in the hands of a few can be counterproductive:

Most of the rivers run out their course unregulated, their marshy banks poisoning the wind... Similarly the uncontrolled use of wealth will multiply vices among men and cause starvation; in brief, such wealth will act like poison. But the selfsame wealth, if its circulation is regulated and its use controlled, can, like a river whose stream has been properly harnessed, promote prosperity” (*CW* 8.337).

The rich are the trustees of the wealth they have (*EW* 389). It is not easy to be a trustee. I need to discipline myself:

My requirements also should be like [that] of the millions. My requirements cannot be greater because I happen to be the son of a rich man. I cannot spend the money [I get from my father] on my pleasures. The man who takes for himself only enough to satisfy the needs customary in his society and spends the rest for social service becomes a trustee (*EW* 403).

The real test of social development is the deepening of the bonds of fellowship among people, going beyond traditional boundaries of caste, creed, etc.

Brotherhood is just now only a distant aspiration. To me it is a test of true spirituality. All our prayers, fasting and observances are empty nothings so long as we do not feel a live kinship with all life. But we have not even arrived at that intellectual belief, let alone a heart realization. We are still selective. A selective brotherhood is a selfish partnership. Brotherhood requires no consideration or response (*EW* 244).

Hence economic disparities that keep people apart cannot be part of authentic development.

The Well-being of the Environment

As the greater part of India is found in her many villages, Gandhi gave great importance to the development of our villages. He believes that “if the village perishes India will perish too. It will be no more India. Her own mission in the world will get lost (*CW* 63.241). It is not merely a concern for economy. For Gandhi a village has a great potential for human development.

Those whose minds are fresh will find new things to see and to learn in villages. It is not true that your mental development becomes stunned when you go to the villages. My reply to those who say this would be that they must have gone there with closed minds. Actually the village, and not the city, is the place for the development of the mind (*Ibid.* 420).

This explains why both in South Africa and in India, Gandhi located his ashram in a rural setting. “The key to swaraj is not in the cities but in the villages” (*Ibid.* 417). I am inclined to believe that Gandhi’s fondness for life in a village is not merely a concern for the vast majority of Indians who live there. It is also an expression of his desire to be with nature.

Our experience of being human is intimately related to our experience of nature around us. For the vast majority of Indians this is what the villages offer:

Villages are normally recognized as significant social units, which are defined and constituted by relationships among villagers themselves, their local deities, and the land on which they live. There should always be harmony between the deities and the population and territory that they protect and rule over, as well as compatibility between the people and their land, whose qualities are ingested by eating food grown in village fields and drinking water drawn from village wells.

This is true of all primal communities, communities that have not been fundamentally disfigured by the impact of modernisation. My experience convinces me that, by and large, the rural folks are much more integrated persons than urban people, even though the former may claim to be more modern, more cultured, more educated. Gandhi too seems to have had a similar impression. “Forest-dwellers everywhere are less often overcome by evil desires than city-dwellers” (CW 33.435).

The symbiotic relation with nature around us is vital for our total health. “A human being is made of earth. His body springs from the earth and derives its sustenance from the various forms which earth takes” (CW 28.206). We instinctively see life as a continuum: the individual is nurtured by the family constituted by blood relations. This is itself a member of a larger family, the world of life around us, and this in turn is sustained by the complex network of non-living realities that surround us. The evolution of the universe and of life upon planet earth tells us that we are born not merely from the womb of our mother, but also from the womb of the earth, from the womb of the cosmos. Just as people around us affect us emotionally, so too life around us shapes our emotions. Nay, even the non-living creatures that constitute our environment—the soil that nourishes our plants and trees, the hills and the valleys, the winds and the clouds, etc., have a significant role in the formation of our emotional make-up, in the discovery of the symbols we need to communicate more intimately, in the genesis of art forms that embody our deeper experiences. Hence we need to be in touch with nature as much as possible, and hence authentic development will not only avoid distancing us from mother earth, but will also safeguard the integrity of creation and promote a more beautiful environment.

Forests are part of our natural resources. Their presence ensures rain and adds to the fertility of the soil, on the other hand “the rainfall is

low wherever there is no vegetation (CW 28.469). We need to protect our forests and engage in the work of afforestation. Hence in some parts of our country “tree plantation would be... a religious necessity” (CW 28.457).

B. Ahimsa: The Ethos of Development

Gandhi concludes his autobiography with the words: “I can say with assurance, as a result of all my experiments, that a perfect vision of Truth can only follow a complete realization of Ahimsa” ((Au 420). Ahimsa “translated ‘love’, is the supreme law for human beings. It knows no exception” (EW 353). For the same reason ahimsa provides the ethos that should guide human development. If ahimsa is understood as love, then it denotes not merely a negative attitude—not hurting others, but a positive task—actively wanting the good of others.

Non-violence towards Oneself

According to popular understanding, industrialization is one essential aspect of development. In an agricultural setup, the farmers need not live together. Their houses can be located on their own land. Even when they do live together, it is in small villages. On the other hand, industrialization means greater concentration of workers. Hence

rapid urbanization is the process that usually accompanies industrialization in the developing countries. There is a mass exodus of peasants, the landless, the destitute and the youth from the villages to the cities... This exodus has created innumerable slums and squatter colonies, which present a pathetic sight of misery and squalor.¹²

What is still more tragic is that “some workplaces are so substandard that people are depersonalized, if not almost dehumanized.”¹³ When the worker returns home after a day of hard labour he is less human than when he left his home for work. Thus the villager who leaves his village in search of job in some way inflicts violence to himself.

We put in more hours of work to earn the money we need to be effective in the consumer market—the other side of development. The pace of life in an urban setup is characterized by acceleration. For instance, our mode of travel is much faster, and “this is considered the

height of civilization” (*HS* 23). All this makes the lives of millions very stressful. This causes bodily and mental sickness. To get some idea of the stress people go through, we just need to travel by the Mumbai local trains during the peak hours, when commuters are either rushing to their work-sites or are returning home. They seem to lose all sense of humanity. Gandhi anticipates this when he speaks of modern cities whose

roadways are traversed by rushing engines dragging numerous cars crowded with men mostly who know not what they are after, who are often absent-minded, and whose tempers do not improve by being uncomfortably packed like sardines in boxes and finding themselves in the midst of utter strangers who would oust them if they could and whom they would in their turn oust similarly (*EW* 97-98).

We are victims of the consumer market because we do not have the inner strength needed to swim against the current. Ahimsa comes to our aid:

Non-violence in its dynamic condition means conscious suffering. It does not mean meek submission to the will of the evil-doer, but it makes the putting of one’s whole soul against the will of the tyrant. Working under this law of our being, it is possible for a single individual to defy the whole might of an unjust empire to save his honour, his religion, his soul and lay the foundation for that empire’s fall or its regeneration (*EW* 238).

Resisting the pressures of our times is an act of true love for oneself. It is also a loving service of others: others can be empowered by what we do.

Non-violence towards Others

Contemporary development promotes competition in all spheres of life. We are once again in the sub-human level of life, where survival of the fittest is the law. “Not killing competition, but life-giving cooperation, is the law of the human beings” (*CW* 61.250). Gandhi rejects the idea that “the Indian population requires to be roused by ‘the lash of competition’ and the other material and sensuous, as well as intellectual, stimuli...” (*EW* 89). Nay, competition leads to unethical tactics: whatever

leads to success is allowed. This leads to the “lowering of standards and regulations governing the interests of labour, consumers and the environment.”¹⁴

The emphasis on capital generation brings about many forms of injustice, that violate human dignity. Let me give just two examples. Many TNCs are either shifting their factories from the First World to the Third World, or are opening new factories in poorer nations—where labour and raw materials are comparatively cheap, and where labour laws are not so stringent—and then exporting the products to richer countries. “The retail price of goods produced in the Third World is often up to 10 times higher than the prices at which the commodity was imported.”¹⁵ The people who work to produce these items and the country whose raw material is used to produce them get very little. This means “the bulk of the earnings of primary producers is appropriated by merchants, intermediaries, wholesalers, and retailers.”¹⁶ Second, if we can replace humans by machines we can save more money. “Between 1972 and 1992 the 500 largest TNCs... laid off 4.4 million workers.”¹⁷ In poorer countries, “workers are forced to endure inhuman working conditions because their governments want to attract elusive foreign investment.”¹⁸

International cooperation involves compromises, and the weaker nations have to accept laws that are not quite fair. Gandhi rejects this way of going about. “It happens these days that many things which are legal are not just. The only right way, therefore, to acquire wealth is to do so rightly. And if that is true, we must know what is just” (*CW* 8.337). What happens between nations, happens within a nation, when poor people have to find jobs. There are so many wanting to work that they are willing to accept the terms of the employer. This too is a form of violence. “It is not enough to live by the laws of demand and supply... God has endowed man with understanding, and with a sense of justice. He must follow these and not think of growing rich by devouring others—by cheating others and reducing them to beggary (*CW* 8.337).

Our inter-connectedness means that we cannot think of development just for our nation. “Love has no boundary. My nationalism includes the love of all the nations of the earth irrespective of creed” (*EW* 245). Richer nations must not only avoid benefitting from the helplessness of poorer nations, but also positively help them in their struggle for

development. This is in their own interests. When peoples experience injustice and have no peaceful way of righting the wrong, then they take to violence. This is one explanation of the growing menace of terrorism and conflicts between the nations. “Present-day capitalists are responsible for widespread and unjust wars. Most of the wars of our times spring from greed for money” (CW 8.371). Unfair developmental approaches are forms of violence, and violence always begets violence.

Non-violence towards the Environment

Unbalanced development has lead to a lot of environmental damage. According to the U.S. Worldwatch Institute, “between 1975 and 2000 20 percent of all living species will have disappeared.”¹⁹ In the last fifty years “we have lost a fifth of the cultivable surface and of the tropical rain forests.”²⁰ Among other problems resulting from our modes of development are acid rains, air and water pollution, destruction of the ozone layer, deforestation and desertification. All these adversely affect human well-being. “Doctors say that 99 per cent of all the diseases are caused by insanitation, by eating things not fit to eat and by lack of proper nutrition... Today pure water, pure earth, and pure air are not available” (CW 85.213). If we wish to be healthy we need to respect the basic laws of life. “Disease springs from a wilful or ignorant breach of the laws of nature” (CW 85.264).

C. Svadeshi: The Resources for Development

In his struggle for India’s independence, Gandhi gave great importance to swadeshi. For many this denotes the use of things—especially cloth—produced in India. For Gandhi, however, this is another way of explaining the unity of human life and the inter-connectedness of all creation. “I would like to apply it [swadeshi] in our religious, political and economic life” (CW 13.251). Swadeshi calls us to bring about harmony in the whole universe, “Swadeshi then means the creation of a most perfect organization in which every part works in perfect harmony with every other” (CW 17.331). This will be possible if we look at the whole of creation as our home. It is an invitation to go beyond narrow boundaries. “In its ultimate and spiritual sense swadeshi stands for the final emancipation of the human soul from its earthly bondage... [which] stands in the way of its realizing its oneness with

other lives. A votary of swadeshi seeks to be emancipated from the bondage of the physical body” (CW 46.254).

Initially swadeshi invites us to take our immediate neighbourhood seriously, to believe that we have within ourselves and within our God-given surroundings the resources we need for development:

Swadeshi carries a greater and profound meaning. It does not mean merely the use of what is produced in one’s own country. That meaning is certainly there in swadeshi. But there is another meaning implied in it which is far greater and much more important. Swadeshi means reliance on our own strength. We should also know what we mean by ‘reliance on our own strength’. ‘Our strength’ means the strength of our body, our mind and our soul (EW 362).

Development reaches its height only when we actualize all our potential. “Human development is about much more than the rise or fall of national incomes. It is about creating an environment in which people can develop their full potential and lead productive, creative lives in accordance with their needs and interests.”²¹

Resources from within Persons

For centuries we Indians have been ruled by outsiders. We have developed some kind of national inferiority complex. We think that what comes from the west is always the best. Also, it is not easy to practise swadeshi, because foreign goods appear to be seductively attractive. Hence swadeshi calls for inner discipline. “Those who are not attached to pleasure and personal adornment, I venture to say, can give a great impetus to *swadeshi*” (EW 364). Real development will give us a sense of confidence, and without it development would only further enslave us.

Swadeshi also calls for the promotion of cottage industries, the spinning wheel being one example. “It supplements agriculture and therefore automatically assists materially to solve the problem of growing poverty. Thus swadeshi is our veritable *Kamadhenu* supplying all our wants and solving many of our difficult problems” (CW 17.331). Our farmers have a lot of free time while they wait for their crops to be ready for harvesting. They can make a more fruitful use of this time. Remaining

idle can also lead to moral problems. Swadeshi will prevent a lot of Indian money from going out of the country (CW 17.470). More positively, “it is capable of limitless expansion and of producing, without any capital outlay, new wealth in the country and providing honourable employment to those who are starving for want of it” (CW 58.445).

Resources from the Society

Swadeshi calls us to be concerned about the people who live in our neighbourhood. “If this interpretation of swadeshi [as oneness with other lives] be correct, then it follows that its votary will as a first duty dedicate himself to the service of his immediate neighbours” (CW 46.254). In doing this he is also reaching out to others. “Pure service of one’s neighbours can never, from its very nature, result in disservice to those who are remotely situated, rather the contrary” (CW 46.354). The resources of a given locality must be used first and foremost to meet the needs of the people of that place. Development enables us to transport our products to places where we can get more money. “Railways have also increased the frequency of famines, because, owing to facility of means of locomotion, people sell out their grain, and it is sent to the dearest markets” (HS 36).²²

We have a large work force. Any form of mechanisation that will leave these people unemployed will be counterproductive.

How can a country with crores of living machines afford to have a machine which will displace the labour of crores of living machines. It would spell their unemployment and their ruin. We have to employ all these crores of living machines... and unless cities decide to depend for the necessities of life and for most of their other needs on the villages, this can never happen (CW 60.256).

The workers will be encouraged if their products find a good market. Hence we need to patronize them.

A votary of swadeshi will carefully study his environment and try to help his neighbours wherever possible by giving preference to local manufactures even if they are of an inferior grade or dearer in price than things manufactured elsewhere. He will try to remedy their defects but will not give them up be-

cause of their defects and take to foreign manufactures” (CW 46.256).

This patronizing of local products is in the long run for the good of all. When our neighbours have a productive job, they have a sense of dignity, and then peace has a better chance.

It would however be a mistake to think that *swadeshi* is a rejection of machine made items or of machinery. “Pure *swadeshi* is not at all opposed to machinery” (EW 366). Machines would be out of place were they to displace the local resources:

Opposition to mills or machinery is not the point. What suits our country most is the point. I am not opposed to the movement of manufacturing machines in the country, nor to making improvements in machinery. I am only concerned with what these machines are meant for. I may ask, in the words of Ruskin, whether these machines will be such as would blow off a million men in a minute or they will be such as would turn waste lands into arable and fertile land (EW 367).

So too, Gandhi is open to the constructive use of modern forms of power. “If we could have electricity in every village home, I should not mind villagers plying their implements and tools with the help of electricity” (EW 401).

Our mother-tongue is one the resources of our society. Hence it “should be given proper importance and its development encouraged” (CW 88.403). This is also true of our culture taken as a whole. So too our ability to rule ourselves. Sad to say, the forces of development are “homogenizing diverse cultural and social sectors and marginalizing the political process.”²³

Resources from the Environment

The more the process of development uses local resources, the greater will be the well-being of the locals. Among different ways to utilize local resources to the maximum, Gandhi suggests the use of organic manure,

made from human and animal excreta... We will then be able to save golden manure worth crores of ru-

pees, which is being wasted because of our ignorance. The soil will become fertile and we will get better crops than what we are getting. As a result we will be rid of famines, crores of people will get enough to eat and the surplus can be exported (CW 90.270).

This manure does not “require expenditure but a little labour” (CW 90.306).

Gandhi was not totally opposed to things of foreign origin. “Boycott of all foreign things is neither possible nor proper” (CW 40.374). The emphasis is on the maximum use of local products. Imported goods should not displace local products. This is the reason why Gandhi insists on khadi: “it is our dharma to use those things which can be or are easily made in our country and on which depends the livelihood of poor people; the boycott of such things and deliberate preference of foreign things is adharma” (CW 40.374). For the same reason we need to use home-made dyes (CW 40.23).

D. Swaraj: The Environment for Development

Gandhi gives us a very simple rule for evaluating developmental activity:

Whenever you are in doubt, or when the self becomes too much with you, apply the following test. Recall the face of the poorest and the weakest man whom you have seen, and ask yourself if the step you contemplate is going to be of any use to him. Will he gain anything by it? Will it restore him to a control over his own life and destiny? In other words, will it lead to swaraj for the hungry and spiritually starving millions? Then you will find your doubts and yourself melting away (EW 418).

Amartya Sen, who received the Nobel Prize for his work on economics, agrees with Gandhi.

Expansion of freedom is viewed... both as the primary end and as the principal means of development. Development consists of the removal of various types of unfreedoms that leave people with little choice and little opportunity of exercising their reasoned agency.

The removal of substantial unfreedoms... is *constitutive* of development.²⁴

Freedom for Persons

Modern development is very much market-related. If the market does not flourish many multinational corporations will collapse. Hence they invest a lot of capital in promoting the sale of their goods, and for this they employ highly sophisticated advertisements that convince many uncritical moderns that they need many more consumer items to be happy. They are brainwashed by the market mafia. They are not really free. “Formerly, men were made slaves under physical compulsion, now they are enslaved by temptation of money and of the luxuries that money can buy” (*HS* 24). Gandhi, on the hand, rejects this craze for more, for the latest. “Civilization, in the real sense of the term, consists not in the multiplication, but in the deliberate and voluntary reduction of wants. This alone promotes real happiness and contentment, and increases the capacity for service” (*EW* 378). He does not “subscribe to the belief that everything old is bad. Truth is old and difficult” (*EW* 399).

To be able to resist the lure of the consumer market, we need to cultivate a critical approach to life, and nurture inner strength that will enable us to resist the superficial glamour of our times. Then we will be free to fulfil our obligations towards others. “Real swarajya consists in restraint. He alone is capable of this who leads a moral life, does not cheat anyone, does not forsake truth and does his duty to his parents, his wife, his children, his servant and his neighbour (*CW* 8.373). Today so many aged parents feel abandoned by their children, who are doing very well in life. They regularly send money to their parents, but have no time for them. We are so taken up by consumer items that we “have hardly leisure for anything else” (*HS* 25), not even for our loved ones. We lose the aesthetic and creative dimensions of being human.

Freedom for Society

According to Gandhi, the development of our villages is the development of our nation. “Independence must begin at the bottom. Thus, every village will be a republic or panchayat having full powers” (*EW* 347). For this the village must be

independent of its neighbours for its own vital wants, and yet interdependent for many others in which dependence is a necessity. Thus every village's first concern will be to grow its own food crops and cotton for its cloth. It should have a reserve for its cattle, recreation and playground for adults and children... The village will maintain a village theatre, school and public hall. It will have its own waterworks, ensuring clean water supply... (*EW* 358-59).

Our villages will be autonomous to the extent our nation is truly independent. With globalisation, weaker nations are forced to compromise on their autonomy. When powerful nations bully the weaker ones, then the latter may retaliate in the way they can. This is one explanation for the growth of international terrorism.

This [permanent peace on earth] is clearly impossible without the great Powers of the earth renouncing their imperialistic design. This again seems impossible without great nations ceasing to believe in soul-destroying competition and to desire to multiply wants and therefore increase their material possessions (*EW* 175).

Years ago I heard a professor of economics, who gave us a lecture on Gandhian economics. He concluded by saying: "Gandhi does not teach us a particular brand of economics. He gives us a comprehensive vision for human growth and development. Only within this framework can we understand and appreciate what he says about economics." I fully agree with this insight. If we disregard the overall Gandhian vision, then what he has to say about economic development sounds nonsensical. But any approach to economic development, that ignores the totality of human well-being, will in the long run be detrimental to human happiness. On the other hand if we follow what Gandhi has to offer then we as a nation will blossom and fulfil our mission.

Ours will then be a truly spiritual nation when we shall show more truth than gold, greater fearlessness than pomp of power and wealth, greater charity than love of self. If we will but clean our houses, our palaces and temples of the attributes of wealth, and show in them the attributes of morality, we can offer battle to any combinations of hostile forces without

having to carry the burden of a heavy militia. Let us seek first the kingdom of God and His righteousness and the irrevocable promise is that everything will be added with us. These are real economics. May you and I treasure them and enforce them in our daily life” (*EW* 99).

What we need is a different way of looking at life. Gandhi believes India can help the world to acquire this vision. “Many of us believe, and I am one of them, that through our civilization we have a message to deliver to the world” (*CW* 13.262). I agree with Gandhi.

Notes

1. Pradeep PILLAI, “India spins its charm”, *The Week*, April 23, 2005, p. 18.
2. Jim ERIKSON, “A Place in the Sun”, *Time*, June 19, 2006, p. 26.
3. *Ibidem*.
4. I shall indicate references to Gandhi’s own writings in the text itself, using an abbreviation, followed by the page number. For *CW*, the volume number will be followed by a point (.) and then the page number. I am basing my study on the following sources:

Au *An Autobiography: The Story of My Experiments with Truth*, Ahmedabad: Navajivan Publishing House, 14th rep, n.d.

CW *The Collected Works of Mahatma Gandhi*, 90 vols., New Delhi: Publication Division, Ministry of Information and Broadcasting, Government of India, 1958-84.

EW *The Essential Writings of Mahatma Gandhi*, ed. Raghavan IYER, New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 1993, 11th rep. 2004.

HS *Indian Home Rule or Hind Swaraj*, Madras: G. A. Natesan, 6th rep., 1947.

When quoting from these books, I have kept the spelling of non-English words as it is in the text. There is also no consistency with regard to the italicizing of these words. Hence they will not be italicized when these texts are quoted.

Certain words—*satya*, *ahi᳚sā*, *svadē᳚a*, *svarâj*, etc.—very frequently used by Gandhi, have become part of the English language. Hence when I use these words, I shall spell them as they are commonly spelt in Gandhi’s writings and not italicize them.

Sometimes the text as it stands appears to have some grammatical error. This could be either because Gandhi himself wrote in a hurry or because the persons who transcribed his talks and speeches did not notice their errors. Whenever possible, I have tried to clarify what Gandhi is saying by supplying some words within square brackets [...].

5. See “Satyagraha: A Theological Model for India”, in Subhash ANAND, *Hindu Inspiration for Christian Reflection: Towards a Hindu-Christian Theology*, Anand (Gujarat): Gujarat Sahitya Prakash, 2004, pp. 171-201, here pp. 179-80.
6. Victor L. ANTHUVAN, *The Dynamics and the Impact of Globalisation: A Subaltern Perspective*, Madurai: Amirtham Pb., 2006, p. 276.
7. Catherine B. HALIBURN, “The Family and the Child: The Asian Family’s Struggle for Life”, *FABC Papers*, 72f, Hongkong: FABC, 1995, p. 5.
8. Nona WALIA, “A family that eats together..”, *Ibid.*, November 5, 2006, p. 2.
9. This sentence is a bit prolematic. I suggest the following reading: “Even if we fail [in terms of economics] in this we shall have succeeded [by maintaining our humanness.”
10. Christopher John FULLER, *The Camphor Flame: Popular Hinduism and Society in India*, New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 1992, p. 128.
11. *Ibidem*.
12. HALIBURN, “The Family and the Child”, p. 13.
13. *Ibid.*, p. 7.
14. ANTHUVAN, *The Dynamics and the Impact of Globalisation*, p. 94.
15. *Ibid.*, p. 77.
16. *Ibidem*.
17. *Ibid.*, p. 83.
18. *Ibid.*, p. 84.
19. Leonardo BOFF, *Ecology and Liberation: A New Paradigm*, Maryknoll (NY): Orbis Books, 1995, p. 15.
20. *Ibidem*.
21. ANTHUVAN, *The Dynamics and the Impact of Globalisation*, p. 285.
22. Gandhi wrote this in 1908. Amartya Sen cites an instance of famine in Wollo (Ethiopia), when food was taken away from Wollo to be sold

elsewhere, “where people had more income to buy food.” Amartya SEN : *Development as Freedom*, New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 1999, p. 167.

23. ANTHUVAN, *The Dynamics and the Impact of Globalisation*, p. 48.
24. SEN : *Development as Freedom*, p. xii. Emphasis in the original.